

Teachers Role in Nep2020 Implementation :Recommendations , Challenges And Suggestions

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Abstract:-

Teachers role is very important to shape the minds of students. Teachers are responsible for the all round and holistic development of students. Teachers need to update themselves with the changing needs of the education world. For quality education knowledge, dedication, passion, quality, skill, professional commitment and motivation of teachers, are the main factors. In the light of NEP 2020, new psychological and pedagogical theories, philosophy, sociology, reformed and reoriented Teacher Education program are required. The present paper discusses in detail about the role of teacher in view of NEP 2020. It also highlights the recommendations given in NEP 2020 for role of teachers, various challenges to be faced in the road of implementations of NEP 2020. Suggestions to overcome these challenges are also given.

Introduction:

The National Education Policy of India's (NEP 2020) main aim is to transform the nation by making improvements in the previous education policy. To make our country's education more inclusive and flexible for future world's needs, NEP 2020 seeks to inculcate 21st century skills like- communication, collaboration, innovation, creative and critical thinking in children. To achieve these goals teachers can play the most important and crucial role. So there is dire need to have impactful teachers who can teach in an effective manner for improving the quality of education in India. The National Education Policy 2020 recommends various changes and modifications in the preparation and role of teachers. There are indeed many challenges to implement the recommendations given in NEP 2020. However the success of the policy depends on the competence of the teachers as they are the ones who will be taking the reforms forward. Further main recommendations of NEP 2020 for teacher's role competence, challenges to be overcome in their implementations and suggestions are as under.

NEP -2020 Recommendations : Use of ICT *

Challenges – Teacher Educators and prospective teachers-

1. To be skilled in both online and offline mode of teaching.
2. To be more technology friendly.
3. Use of Smart Boards and flipped classrooms (blended learning).
4. To use virtual reality and cloud computing for teaching.
5. Use of resource available (online open and resources)

Suggestions –

1. Orient, train and equip Teacher Educators & pupil teachers with competence to use ICT.

2. Train TE & PTs to use smart boards, various tools of technology, use of 3 D technology, cloud computing, find information and instructional material available online (nroer).
3. Workshop to learn the use of ICT (in teaching, learning and evaluation) , preparation of lesson plan for online mode , learn different virtual teaching aids, preparation of online tests etc.

NEP -2020 Recommendations : 2- Communication Skills (Listening, speaking, reading and writing)

Challenges –

1. How to enrich the vocabulary and language proficiency of prospective teachers?
2. How to enhance verbal, non-verbal communication skill and dynamic interaction in prospective teachers?

Suggestions –

1. Language proficiency (written and speaking) courses in B.Ed.
2. 2-Organize discussion, debate, seminar, sharing of experiences, reflective thinking, writing reflection, Field note etc.
3. 3-Train students / teachers in each of the four (physical, linguistic, cognitive, social and emotional) communication skills by explicit teaching model and praise.

NEP -2020 Recommendations : 3- Multidisciplinary and integrated approach*

Challenges –

1. Categories of teachers- We have Music, Dance, Art, Craft, Activity teachers in one group, Hindi Sanskrit another, Physical Education a third, Physics Chemistry Maths, a fourth, Social science and General Science yet another without adequate vertical and horizontal integration.
2. It is typical for a Physical education teacher or an art craft or Sanskrit teacher to say that there

is no need for IT or ICT for her/him. All these must change.

Suggestions –

1. Every Teacher must be brought on a standardized platform as far as certain common skills are concerned irrespective of their teaching subjects and levels of teaching.
2. There is a need to equip teachers to overcome their biases in these regards and positively handle these challenges.

NEP -2020 Recommendations: 4-Positive Learning Environment in school (Safe, inclusive, Effective Teaching Environment)*

Challenges –

- a)- How to train teachers to be part of an inclusive community with a common goal to achieve that all children are learning.
- b)-Constructing a sensitive and inclusive culture for effective learning.
- c)-To develop human & social sensitivity and consciousness in prospective teachers for believing and practicing equity, equality and inclusiveness.

Suggestions –

1. Train prospective teachers to understand the socio –cultural needs of
2. Students and to deal with contemporary issues of diverse learners.
3. Need to train and equip prospective teachers to handle classroom with diverse, socio-economic, intelligence, special children, multilingual and multicultural students.

NEP -2020 Recommendations : 5-Medium of instruction*

The policy encourages local languages to be the medium of instruction at least up to Grade 5, promotes bi-lingual education and textbooks for learning; as well as multiple languages at middle and secondary levels.

Challenges –

There is no definitive decision or guideline around the language of instruction. For example, the policy says to use local languages '*wherever possible*', which leaves a lot of room for the status quo— which is the existing three language formula -to continue, especially in the case of the high-performing government run school systems such as (KVs).

Suggestions –

According to the NEP-2020, students of the private schools will be introduced with English at a much earlier age than the students of the Government schools. The academic syllabus will be taught in the respective regional languages of the Government school students. This is one of the major new education policy drawbacks as this will increase the number of students uncomfortable in communicating in English thus widening the gap between sections of the societies.

NEP -2020 Recommendations : 6-More Autonomy for teachers to Choose curriculum and teaching methods*

Challenges –

1. As there is prescribed syllabus and text book for each class. How do prospective teachers learn to choose curriculum, No training is provided for that.
2. Demo lessons (given by the TE) and simulated teaching (by PTs) are given very less time during B.Ed. course.
3. Only lecture and demonstration methods are taught and practiced by prospective teachers during the training.

Suggestions –

1. 1-Training to prospective teachers related to curriculum construction and concept mapping.
2. 2-Prospective teachers to be trained to freely experiment with various teaching methods and share feedback (success as well as failures)
3. 3-More Demo lessons by TE using different methods and simulated teaching by PTs using different teaching skills should be practiced in pre-internship phase.

NEP -2020 Recommendations : 7-Respecting individual differences in pupil teachers *

Challenges –

Respecting individual differences in pupil teachers as well as within teacher educators -Teachers too like students have individual differences, like and dislikes.

Suggestions –

It is important to consider these differences in both the cases and provide teachers with more autonomy to choose a programme beneficial to them.

NEP -2020 Recommendations : 8-Formation of school complex

(Participation of school/ teachers in community service, adult and vocational education)*

Challenges –

1. a)- Building a lively teacher community relationship.
2. b)-Designing a curriculum connected to real world experience.
3. c-)Cross generation learning
4. d)-Local community involvement in designing solutions to local problems.
5. e)- Reaching all stake holders.

Suggestions –

1. Train prospective teachers for experiential learning.
2. Training to prospective teachers to communicate and encourage to ask for mentoring (through field visit, street plays, awareness programme ,survey, report writing ,project based learning etc.) and seek support from society.

3. Train prospective teachers to work with local business, subject expert to connect core curriculum to outside world and given action research project to design engaging learning experience in and out of the CR.

NEP -2020 Recommendations : 9- Training and Internship *

Challenges –

1. To manage 120 days internship in one year B.Ed. (after PG) is a great challenge. How to manage it in 4 years B.Ed. Program?
2. Finding the schools for Internship.
3. Support from school principal and subject teacher (mentor).

Suggestions –

1. Duration of microteaching to be increased in first year.
2. All microteaching skills to be practiced by pupil teacher upto perfection.
3. Simulated teaching to be essential part of pre internship.
4. Teaching internship /apprentice to be scheduled in last semester so that student get placement and earn stipend. It will motivate them to learn and perform better .
5. Internship at hometown to be allowed so that student learns to teach through their own language, local art and cultural heritage.
6. 6-State Govt. education dept. should allot school for internship to each TEIs.

NEP -2020 Recommendations : 10 -Role of National Testing Agency *

Challenges

- 1-How to set criteria for selection in B.Ed. course?
 - 2-Criteria for recruitment of teachers.
- How to select efficient, passionate and instructional leader, who is empathetic, feels invested in the community and can act as curriculum designer too?

Suggestions –

- 1-Students need to be tested on their teaching aptitude, good communication skills, organizational skills, innovating skills, enthusiastic and empathetic nature.
- 2-For selection of teacher the process needs to be conducted in different phases –
 1. written test
 2. teaching proficiency
 3. interview
- 3-Interview needs to be an integral part of teacher selection process to assess passion, comfort and proficiency in teaching in English /Hindi as well as in the local language.
- 4-Teachers to be tested on the following criteria -
 1. leadership qualities
 2. technology savy
 3. innovative
 4. entrepreneurial skills and
 5. problem solving skills.

NEP -2020 Recommendations : 11-In-service continuous professional

Development (Strengthening Teachers* Challenges

- 1- Organising training, Orientation and Refresher Courses.

- 2-Time & Resource Management

- 3- Availability / hiring Experts & Resource Persons

Suggestions –

1. 1-Teacher should be encouraged to join courses related to education teaching skills & professional development (i.e. PGDSL, PGDEMA, Certificate in English language, Guidance and counseling, use of ICT etc.)offered by IGNOU SWAYAM, MOOC, Deeksha etc. along with regular teaching.
2. 2-Work shop for teachers strengthening communication skills, ICT skills, visual presentation skills (use of visual tools like graphic organizer, flow charts, venn diagrams and concept maps).
3. 3-Training programmers on personality development & behaviour management.
4. 4-Training on use of ICT for record keeping, proper follow up and feedback of students and peers by using e-mails, whatsapp, twitter, facebook, blog etc.

Conclusion:

Education and teachers should be the key players in the successful implementation of NEP 2020.If not implemented in an effective and well planned manner ,the policy recommendations and dialogues will just remain on paper and in the workshops and discussion rooms.Now teachers have to prepare themselves to play the role of being facilitators of NEP 2020. To ensure that the developmental goals of policy are met ,teachers have to adopt innovative strategies in class rooms .Teachers have to prepare themselves to promote and create environment where students can think with a creative, critical ,logical and innovative mindsets. Teachers have to receive training to identify the development needs of each individual student in their class rooms.

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